
Peer-assisted reading programs for EFL low-proficiency learners

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Annotation

This paper investigates the efficacy of Peer-Assisted Reading (PAR) strategies for low-proficiency English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners within a technical university context. Specifically targeting students from the faculties of Economics, Aerospace Technology, and Material Science at 'TIAME' National Research University, the study proposes a collaborative pedagogical framework to enhance reading comprehension and vocabulary acquisition. According to Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis, negative emotions like anxiety, low motivation, or lack of confidence can block language learning. Working with peers in a structured way helps reduce these barriers by offering social support, shared responsibility, and quick help during reading, which gives students more chances to learn from meaningful input. Drawing on social interdependence theory and recent research on reading anxiety, the paper argues that structured peer interaction – combined with the use of Graded Readers and digital vocabulary tools – can mitigate the affective filter and improve engagement. Preliminary findings suggest that PAR significantly aids in bridging the proficiency gap for engineering and economics students, fostering both linguistic competence and the soft skills essential for their future professional careers.

Keywords

Peer-assisted learning, EFL reading, collaborative strategies, low-proficiency learners, graded readers

Ingliz tili darslarida past o'zlashtiruvchi talabalar uchun tengdoshlar ko'magida o'qish dasturlari

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Annotatsiya *Chet tilini o'rganuvchi past darajadagi talabalar uchun tengdoshlar ko'magida o'qish dasturlari Ushbu maqola texnika universiteti sharoitida ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'rganayotgan past darajadagi talabalar uchun tengdoshlar ko'magida o'qish strategiyalarining samaradorligini o'rganadi. Tadqiqot xususan, "TIQXMMI" Milliy tadqiqot universitetining Iqtisodiyot, Aerokosmik texnologiyalar va Materialshunoslik fakultetlari talabalariga qaratilgan bo'lib, o'qishni tushunish va so'z boyligini oshirish uchun hamkorlikdagi pedagogik tizimni taklif etadi. Krashenning Affektiv Filtr Gipotezasiga ko'ra, xavotir, past motivatsiya yoki ishonchsizlik kabi salbiy his-tuyg'ular til o'rganishga to'sqinlik qilishi mumkin. Tengdoshlar bilan tizimli ravishda ishlash ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlash, umumiy mas'uliyat va o'qish paytida tezkor yordam berish orqali bu to'siqlarni kamaytirishga yordam beradi, bu esa o'quvchilarga mazmunli ma'lumotlardan ko'proq o'rganish imkoniyatini beradi. Ijtimoiy o'zaro bog'liqlik nazariyasi va o'qishdagi xavotir bo'yicha so'nggi tadqiqotlarga asosanib, maqolada darajalangan o'quv qo'llanmalari va raqamli lug'at vositalaridan foydalangan holda tashkil etilgan tuzilmaviy tengdoshlar o'zaro ta'siri affektiv to'siqlarni kamaytirishi va mashg'ulotlarga qiziqishni oshirishi ta'kidlanadi. Dastlabki natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, tengdoshlar ko'magida o'qish dasturlari muhandislik va iqtisodiyot yo'nalishi talabalari uchun bilim darajasidagi bo'shliqni to'ldirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etib, ularning kelajakdagi kasbiy faoliyati uchun zarur bo'lgan ham til, ham yumshoq ko'nikmalarni rivojlantiradi.*

Kalit so'zlar *Tengdoshlar yordamida o'qitish, o'qish, hamkorlik strategiyalari, past darajadagi o'quvchilar, darajalangan o'quv qo'llanmalari*

Программы чтения с помощью сверстников для студентов с низким уровнем владения английским языком

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Аннотация *Программы чтения с помощью сверстников для студентов с низким уровнем владения английским языком. В данной статье исследуется эффективность стратегий чтения с помощью сверстников для студентов с низким уровнем владения английским языком как иностранным в контексте технического университета. Исследование, ориентированное на студентов факультетов экономики, аэрокосмических технологий и материаловедения НИУ «ТИИИМСХ», предлагает совместную*

педагогическую структуру для улучшения понимания прочитанного и расширения словарного запаса. Согласно гипотезе аффективного фильтра Крашена, негативные эмоции, такие как тревога, низкая мотивация или неуверенность в себе, могут препятствовать изучению языка. Работа со сверстниками в структурированном формате помогает снизить эти барьеры, предлагая социальную поддержку, разделение ответственности и быструю помощь во время чтения, что дает учащимся больше возможностей учиться на основе осмысленной информации. Опираясь на теорию социальной взаимозависимости и последние исследования тревожности при чтении, в статье утверждается, что структурированное взаимодействие сверстников – в сочетании с использованием адаптированных книг и цифровых словарных инструментов – может снизить аффективный фильтр и повысить вовлеченность. Предварительные выводы показывают, что значительно помогает преодолеть разрыв в уровне владения языком у студентов инженерных и экономических специальностей, способствуя развитию как языковой компетенции, так и гибких навыков, необходимых для их будущей профессиональной карьеры.

**Ключевые
слова**

Обучение при помощи сверстников, чтение, стратегии сотрудничества, учащиеся с низким уровнем подготовки, адаптированная литература

Introduction

As global engineering and economics continue to change, English skills are essential for academic and career success. At 'TIAME' NRU, students must read complex technical texts early in their studies. Many, however, start with low English proficiency (CEFR A1-A2), which makes reading academic materials on their own stressful and frustrating. This paper looks at the teaching needs of undergraduates from three faculties at "TIAME" NRU: Economics (14 students), Aerospace Technology and Sustainable Development (10 students), and Material Science and Technology of New Materials (10 students). These fields require strong reading skills to access international standards, reports, and manuals. Traditional teacher-centered methods often do not engage students with low English skills, which can make them passive in class. To help with this issue, we suggest using Peer-Assisted Reading (PAR) programs. PAR encourages students to work together

instead of struggling alone. Recent research shows that choosing the right reading strategies and using code-switching can help students understand better in multilingual classrooms (Azimova & Surmanov, 2025). By combining these ideas with proven collaborative learning methods, this paper presents a framework to lower reading anxiety and improve vocabulary through peer support.

Theoretical framework and Literature

Review Social Interdependence and Peer Learning Peer-Assisted Learning (PAL) is based on Social Interdependence Theory, which says that when group members rely on each other, they interact in ways that help everyone learn (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). In EFL classrooms, students who work together to understand a text use "exploratory talk" to build understanding that they could not reach alone. This idea matches Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), where a peer helps another student move from their

current skill level to a higher one (Vygotsky, 1978).

Reading anxiety is different from general language anxiety (Saito et al., 1999). For engineering and science students, it often gets worse because of technical words and complex sentences. Studies show that high anxiety can block learning (Solati, 2024). Collaborative Strategic Reading (CSR) helps reduce this anxiety by sharing the work among group members, making reading feel less overwhelming (Zoghi et al., 2010).

For students with low English skills, real technical texts are often too hard. Graded Readers, which use simpler words and structures, are very important. Studies show that Graded Readers give students the "comprehensible input" (i+1) they need to build fluency and confidence before moving on to harder texts (Horst, 2005; Waring & Takaki, 2003). Research at TIAME NRU also found that Graded Readers help improve reading skills, even for students in fields like law, which also requires precise terms (Surmanov, 2024).

A balanced reading approach is important. Extensive reading, which means reading a lot of easy texts, helps build fluency. Intensive reading, which means closely studying short texts, helps build accuracy (Grabe & Stoller, 2011). Egamovich (2022) says both methods work well together, but for students with low English skills, starting with extensive reading and peer support can be more motivating.

Learning new words is a big challenge for students with low English skills. Memorizing lists usually does not help them remember words for long (Nation, 2013). Newer methods suggest using digital tools like Anki, which use spaced repetition to help students remember better (Egamovich, 2025). When these tools are used in a peer-assisted reading group, students can quiz each other on vocabulary, which helps them remember through social practice.

Methodology

This Participatory Action Research (PAR) intervention was designed to meet the

language needs of first-year students at "TIAME" National Research University. The study included 34 students with low English proficiency, identified through entry-level tests. They came from the Faculty of Economics (14 students), Aerospace Technology and Sustainable Development (10 students), and Material Science and Technology of New Materials (10 students). To make learning relevant, each group used materials related to their field. Economics students read about market principles, while technical students worked with simplified texts on physics and sustainability. Anki software was used to help students manage and remember new vocabulary (Egamovich, 2025).

The main teaching approach was Reciprocal Teaching, a collaborative method that helps students support each other's learning (Klingner & Vaughn, 1996). Students were paired to balance different language strengths, such as vocabulary and grammar, to support peer learning. Each pair followed a set process: predicting, questioning, clarifying, and summarizing the technical texts. Because Uzbekistan is multilingual, students were allowed to use Uzbek or Russian during the clarification step to help explain difficult ideas (Azimova & Surmanov, 2025). This approach helped fill in gaps in understanding without losing sight of the academic goals. At the end of each cycle, pairs used their own Anki decks to quiz each other and reinforce the new technical vocabulary they had learned.

Discussion of Implications Using Participatory Action Research (PAR) strategies helps reduce the high levels of foreign language anxiety that engineering students often feel when reading technical English texts (Saito et al., 1999). When students work in pairs, the focus moves from individual performance to group problem-solving, which lowers the fear of making mistakes in front of others. This group approach creates a supportive environment where students feel comfortable trying out complex language and asking questions they might avoid in a traditional

classroom. As a result, working together not only builds social connections but also gives students the confidence to take more risks and engage with difficult material.

Teaching reading strategies in a peer-led setting helps students move from passively receiving information to actively thinking about what they read. This approach supports Surmanov's (2025) view that good academic reading depends on an active relationship between the reader and the text. When students use strategies like predicting and questioning in groups, they are encouraged to share their thinking out loud.

A key part of this process is the "protégé effect," where teaching or explaining a concept to a peer leads to deeper understanding. When students take on the role of teacher, they have to organize their thoughts clearly and notice any gaps in their knowledge, which helps them learn better (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). This back-and-forth ensures that understanding comes from working together, not just from reading alone.

Adding digital tools like Anki to the reading curriculum helps students learn new vocabulary more effectively. Egamovich (2025) points out that remembering words well depends on regular and organized review, which can be hard to do alone. Anki's spaced-repetition system gives students the structure they need to remember vocabulary for the long term.

In the PAR approach, working with others helps students stay motivated and avoid dropping out of self-study. They are responsible to their partners for learning the shared Anki decks. This shared responsibility turns a usually solo task into a group effort, making sure students keep up with the regular review needed to remember technical vocabulary.

Students in Aerospace and Material Science need strong skills to understand technical documents, which are essential for their future careers. However, there is often a gap between general English skills and the

specific language needed for their fields. Graded Readers help bridge this gap by making it easier for students to move into academic language (Surmanov, 2024).

Using simplified texts on topics like "The History of Flight" or "Properties of Metals" helps students gradually build the vocabulary they need for their major subjects. This step-by-step approach keeps students from feeling overwhelmed by separating tough concepts from complicated language. In the end, it prepares them to read real engineering texts without facing a difficult starting point.

Conclusion

Peer-Assisted Reading (PAR) programs at "TIAME" NRU offer a practical way to address the challenges faced by low-proficiency EFL learners in technical and economic fields. By combining collaborative learning with materials like Graded Readers and digital vocabulary tools, teachers can create a strong learning environment. This method helps students develop both general and technical English skills and builds a supportive atmosphere that boosts their academic confidence. In the end, these strategies give students the tools they need to handle the demands of their future professions.

For students in Economics, Aerospace, and Material Science, the Peer-Assisted Reading (PAR) approach does two things: it helps them improve their reading skills and also shows them how to work together, just like they will in their future jobs. Through organized peer activities, students practice the teamwork and communication they will need in their careers.

We suggest that language teachers at "TIAME" NRU move away from traditional lectures and instead use interactive, student-focused methods. This change better supports both the emotional and learning needs of students compared to older teaching styles.

Future research should look at these methods over a longer period. It is important to find out how PAR and scaffolded materials affect students' ability to understand real,

complex technical texts in their fields. This kind of research would show whether Graded

Readers and peer-assisted strategies have lasting benefits.

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